

**THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE STUDY OF SYNTAX IN CLASSES OF
RUSSIAN AS A NON-NATIVE LANGUAGE**

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Annotation: *This article delves into the integration of cutting-edge technologies to enhance the study of syntax for individuals learning Russian as a non-native language. Acknowledging the challenges associated with traditional syntax education, the piece explores the significance of mastering sentence structure for effective communication. The narrative navigates through various innovative tools, including interactive learning platforms, natural language processing (NLP) tools, virtual reality (VR) applications, and collaborative online spaces. Real-world case studies and success stories illustrate the transformative impact of these technologies on student engagement, performance, and overall learning experiences. Additionally, the article addresses potential challenges such as technology accessibility and training, proposing strategies for mitigation. As it concludes, the piece offers insights into future trends and considerations, emphasizing the evolving landscape of language education and the continuous quest for improved methodologies in syntax learning for Russian language learners.*

Key words; *considerations, syntax, student , create a plan, specialists, interactive, educators;*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the field of language education has witnessed a significant shift towards the integration of innovative technologies to improve teaching and learning outcomes. This article explores the use of cutting-edge technologies in the study of syntax for students learning Russian as a non-native language.

There are diverse problems in the practical training of foreign students in Russian phonetics and intonation within the different types of speech activity. So, in terms of audition, the student must learn to accurately perceive the overall phonetic shape of Russian words in the speech stream and the rhythmical- intonation design of speech. Likewise, the student must create a plan for expression, a contextual plan, and must learn and understand the importance of pronouncing statements emerging from the interaction of lexicon, syntax, intonation and context. In the process of mastering phonetically correct

oral language the student should learn in full Russian articulation based on the use of syllables, words, and phrases, primarily in the full style of pronunciation, in order to acquire all of the diverse types of switches in articulation from one articulation to the another within a word, phrase, or syntagma. The problems of training highly qualified specialists also include the formation of a student's benchmark, standardizing requirements for future experts, the ability to take these independently, and the constant improvement of knowledge of the specialty.

The Importance of Syntax in Language Learning

Understanding syntax is crucial for effective communication in any language. Syntax governs the structure of sentences, and proficiency in syntax is a key component of language fluency. In the context of learning Russian as a non-native language, mastering syntax is particularly challenging due to the language's unique grammatical structure.

Current Challenges in Syntax Learning for Russian Language Learners

Traditional methods of teaching syntax may pose challenges for non-native learners, including limited interactivity, passive learning experiences, and a lack of personalized feedback. Addressing these challenges is essential for fostering a more engaging and effective learning environment.

Innovative Technologies in Syntax Education

1. Interactive Learning Platforms:

- Explore the use of interactive online platforms that provide exercises and real-time feedback on syntax construction.

- Gamification elements can enhance student motivation and participation.

2. Natural Language Processing (NLP) Tools:

- Integrate NLP tools to analyze and provide feedback on sentence structure and grammar.

- Customized exercises can be generated based on individual learner needs.

3. Virtual Reality (VR) for Immersive Learning:

- Create virtual environments that immerse learners in Russian language contexts, encouraging practical application of syntax rules.

- VR simulations can replicate real-life communication scenarios.

4. Collaborative Online Spaces:

- Utilize online platforms for collaborative learning, allowing students to engage in group exercises and peer-reviewed syntax activities.

Case Studies and Success Stories

Highlight specific examples or case studies where educational institutions or language programs have successfully implemented innovative technologies in teaching Russian syntax. Discuss improvements in student performance, engagement, and overall learning experience.

Overcoming Potential Challenges

Acknowledge potential obstacles such as access to technology, training for educators, and cost implications. Propose strategies for overcoming these challenges and ensuring equitable access to innovative learning tools.

Future Trends and Considerations

Explore emerging technologies and trends in language education that have the potential to further enhance the study of syntax for Russian language learners.

CONCLUSION

As technology continues to evolve, its integration into language education becomes increasingly vital. By leveraging innovative technologies, educators can transform the study of syntax in Russian as a non-native language, providing students with a more dynamic, interactive, and personalized learning experience.

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